

A Mathematical Framework for Estimating Tumour Age Using Ki-67 and Mitotic Figures

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Abstract

Tumour pathology assessment has traditionally relied heavily on spatial information at a single time point, such as tumour size and morphology, while the temporal aspect of tumour growth has not been explicitly addressed. However, tumour progression is inherently a time-dependent biological process, and a conceptual framework is needed to infer tumour dynamics from routinely available morphological data.

Ki-67 labelling index and mitotic counts, both widely used in diagnostic pathology, reflect cell cycle activity but are typically interpreted as independent static indicators. In this study, we propose a mathematical framework that integrates the ratio of Ki-67-positive cells to mitotic figures to estimate the elapsed time from a single transformed cell to the observed tumour size, referred to here as “tumour age.”

Furthermore, by incorporating cell size and tumour cell area fraction (α), the model accounts for differences in cellular packing density within tissue. A pilot application to representative tumour cases (breast carcinoma) suggested a consistent relationship between histological proliferative features and the estimated tumour age.

This framework provides a conceptually simple and practically implementable approach for introducing a temporal dimension into routine pathological assessment. Future integration of additional factors, such as necrosis and fibrosis, may serve as a basis for a more dynamic understanding of tumour biology.

Keywords: Tumour age, Cell cycle dynamics, Ki-67, Mitotic index, Mathematical model, Histopathology, Tumour progression

Introduction

In current pathological practice, the temporal dimension of tumours is not explicitly quantified, and diagnosis is primarily based on spatial information such as tumour extent and morphology. However, tumour growth and progression *in vivo* are inherently time-dependent processes. If the rate of tumour progression could be quantitatively estimated, it would provide a new perspective for treatment selection and prognostic assessment.

In particular, in tumour types in which proliferative activity is routinely evaluated—such as breast carcinoma, neuroendocrine tumours, and gastrointestinal stromal tumours—Ki-67 labelling index and mitotic count are widely used as indicators of cell proliferation. Ki-67 is expressed throughout all active phases of the cell cycle (G1, S, G2, and M phases) but is absent in the quiescent phase (G0) [1]. In contrast, mitotic figures reflect only cells in the mitotic (M) phase. Mitotic count is commonly used as a marker of proliferative activity in many tumour types and constitutes a key component of histological grading systems, such as the Nottingham grading system in breast carcinoma [2].

Although both indicators reflect tumour proliferative capacity, they are typically interpreted as static measures, and their temporal implications have not been fully explored. Furthermore, while they are often described and interpreted independently in routine practice, they may in fact represent different projections of the same underlying cellular dynamics.

In this study, we propose a conceptual mathematical framework to estimate the time required for a tumour to grow from a single transformed cell to its observed size, referred to here as “tumour age,” based on the ratio of Ki-67-positive cells to mitotic figures.

Within this framework, tumour age is estimated by integrating proliferative activity with spatial structure, thereby linking microscopic cellular dynamics to macroscopic tumour size.

This study represents an attempt to reinterpret pathological indicators within a generalized mathematical framework and to reconsider pathology from a physics-based perspective that incorporates the temporal dimension.

Methods

The symbols used in the equations and discussions in this study are defined as follows:

R : tumour radius [mm]

r : tumour cell radius [mm]

$N_{\text{Ki-67}}$: number of Ki-67-positive tumour cells

N_{mit} : number of mitotic figures

T : cell cycle duration [h]

τ_M : M-phase duration [h]

V : tumour volume [mm³]

v : volume of a single tumour cell [mm³]

As a conceptual model, the tumour is approximated as a sphere with radius R [mm], assuming that tumour cells are densely and uniformly packed within it (Figure 1A). A correction reflecting actual tumour architecture is introduced later.

If the radius of a tumour cell is r [mm], the total number of tumour cells can be expressed as the ratio of volumes:

$$\frac{\frac{4}{3}\pi R^3}{\frac{4}{3}\pi r^3} = \left(\frac{R}{r}\right)^3 \text{ [cells]} \quad \dots \textcircled{1}$$

Assuming that a single tumour cell of radius r divides into two cells over a cell cycle of duration T [h], the number of cells grows exponentially. After n cell cycles (nT), the number of cells becomes 2^n .

Let t [h] denote the time required for the tumour to reach $(R/r)^3$ cells. Since $t = nT$,

$$2^n = \left(\frac{R}{r}\right)^3$$
$$n = \log_2 \left(\left(\frac{R}{r}\right)^3 \right) = 3 \log_2 \left(\frac{R}{r} \right)$$
$$t = nT = 3T \log_2 \left(\frac{R}{r} \right) \text{ [h]} \quad \dots \textcircled{2}$$

Estimation of Cell Cycle Duration

Next, the cell cycle duration T [h] is approximated from the number of Ki-67–positive tumour cells (using absolute counts rather than labelling index) and the number of mitotic figures within the same high-power field under light microscopy.

Since Ki-67 labels cells in all active phases of the cell cycle (G1, S, G2, and M phases), mitotic cells are included among Ki-67–positive cells. Therefore, the ratio of mitotic figures to Ki-67–positive cells reflects the fraction of time spent in the mitotic phase of the cell cycle (Figure 2).

Although the duration of the cell cycle varies depending on cell type and conditions, the average duration of the mitotic phase (M phase) has been reported to be approximately 1 hour [3,4]. Assuming that Ki-67–positive cells are uniformly distributed across all phases of the cell cycle within the same field—that is, the proportion of cells in each phase remains constant over time (steady state)—we obtain:

$$\frac{N_{\text{mit}}}{N_{\text{Ki-67}}} = \frac{\tau_M}{T}$$

$$\tau_M \approx 1 \text{ hour}$$

$$T = \frac{N_{\text{Ki-67}}}{N_{\text{mit}}} \quad [\text{h}] \quad \dots \textcircled{3}$$

Thus, the ratio of mitotic figures to Ki-67–positive cells represents the fraction of time occupied by the M phase within the cell cycle.

Combining (2) and (3), the time required for the tumour to reach its current size (*radius* R [mm]) is given by:

$$t = \frac{N_{\text{Ki-67}}}{N_{\text{mit}}} \cdot 3 \log_2 \left(\frac{R}{r} \right) \quad [\text{h}] \quad \dots \textcircled{4}$$

In this model, tumour cells are assumed to be densely and uniformly distributed in space, i.e., a three-dimensional “packed” configuration. However, in actual tumours,

cellular distribution is often sparse and heterogeneous due to the presence of glandular structures and stromal components such as fibrosis. Such structural heterogeneity may affect the assumption of spatial scaling.

To address this, we define the area fraction of tumour cells observed in a microscopic field as α ($0 \leq \alpha \leq 1$), and assume that the internal tumour structure is statistically isotropic. Under this assumption, a correction is introduced to account for three-dimensional cellular density.

Since the area fraction α is a two-dimensional quantity, and assuming an isotropic random distribution of tumour structure, the reduction in density along each spatial dimension can be approximated as $\alpha^{1/2}$. Under this approximation, the three-dimensional volumetric density can be expressed as:

$$(\alpha^{1/2})^3 = \alpha^{3/2}$$

Therefore, by multiplying $\alpha^{3/2}$ to the cell number estimate based on tumour radius ($\propto R^3$), a correction for the effective tumour cell density is introduced. Incorporating this correction, equation (4) can be reformulated as:

$$t = \frac{N_{\text{Ki-67}}}{N_{\text{mit}}} \log_2 \left(\left(\frac{R}{r} \right)^3 \alpha^{3/2} \right) \quad [\text{h}] \quad \dots \textcircled{5}$$

This correction allows the model to reflect the actual distribution density of tumour cells within the tumour parenchyma, thereby enabling a more realistic estimation of tumour age.

A schematic representation of Ki-67–positive cells, Ki-67–negative cells, and mitotic figures within a tumour cell population is shown in Figure 1B.

In this model, the area fraction of tumour cells at the time of observation, denoted as α , is introduced as an indicator of effective cellular density and used as a correction factor for the required number of cell divisions.

However, α represents a composite parameter reflecting multiple morphological processes, including gland formation, stromal reaction, necrosis, and cell loss. The time required for these processes is not explicitly incorporated into the present model.

In this study, α at the time of observation is used as a static approximation. The incorporation of its temporal evolution, $\alpha(t)$, into a dynamic model remains an important subject for future investigation.

Let the nuclear radius be r_{nuc} and the nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratio be ρ . The cell radius r can then be expressed as:

$$r = r_{\text{nuc}} \rho^{-1/2}$$

Substituting this into equation (5), we obtain:

$$t = \frac{N_{\text{Ki-67}}}{N_{\text{mit}}} \log_2 \left\{ \left(\frac{R}{r_{\text{nuc}}} \right)^3 \alpha^{3/2} \rho^{3/2} \right\} \quad [h] \quad \dots \textcircled{6}$$

Furthermore, generalizing this formulation, let the tumour volume be V [mm^3] and the volume of a single tumour cell be v [mm^3].

The present model is based on a first-order approximation that treats tumour growth as a steady-state process, and temporal variations in growth rate may contribute to estimation error.

$$t = \frac{N_{\text{Ki-67}}}{N_{\text{mit}}} \log_2 \left\{ \left(\frac{V}{v} \right) \alpha^{3/2} \right\} \quad [h] \quad \dots \textcircled{7}$$

The proposed mathematical framework was preliminarily applied to representative cases to evaluate its feasibility. For image analysis, cell size and cellular area density were measured using cellSens (Olympus, Tokyo, Japan) and Fiji (ImageJ, NIH, USA).

The nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratio (ρ) was calculated by randomly selecting ten representative tumour cells and averaging the ratio of nuclear area to total cell area.

Obvious outliers, considered to be measurement artifacts, were excluded from the calculation of representative values.

Results

Using the proposed model, tumour age was estimated for two representative cases of invasive ductal carcinoma, along with two corresponding simulated cases for comparison. The tumour radius R and nuclear radius r_{nuc} were calculated as one-half of the measured tumour diameter and nuclear diameter, respectively.

Case 1

Invasive ductal carcinoma, histological grade I.

The tumour diameter was 10.0 mm, the mean nuclear diameter was 6.7 μm , and the nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratio (ρ) was approximately 0.90. The cellular area fraction (α) was estimated to be approximately 0.78. The numbers of Ki-67-positive cells and mitotic figures were approximately 120 and 2, respectively. Substituting these values into equation (5), the tumour age was estimated to be approximately 77.2 days (Figure 3A).

Simulation Model 1

Invasive ductal carcinoma, histological grade II.

The tumour diameter was 10.0 mm, the mean nuclear diameter was 7.5 μm , and the nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratio (ρ) was approximately 0.90. The cellular area fraction (α) was estimated to be approximately 0.98. The numbers of Ki-67-positive cells and mitotic figures were the same as in Case 1 (120 and 2, respectively). Based on equation (5), the estimated tumour age was also approximately 77.2 days.

In equation (6), the term $\left(\frac{R}{r_{\text{nuc}}}\right)^3$ represents the effect of nuclear size, whereas $\alpha^{3/2}$ represents the effects of cellular packing density. Since the N/C ratio (ρ) was identical in both cases, the observed similarity in estimated tumour age suggests that the nuclear size and packing density (α) may act in a compensatory manner.

Case 2

Invasive ductal carcinoma, histological grade I.

The tumour diameter was 10.0 mm, the mean nuclear diameter was 10.0 μm , and the nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratio (ρ) was approximately 0.74. The cellular area fraction (α) was estimated to be approximately 0.55. The numbers of Ki-67-positive cells and mitotic figures were approximately 100 and 2, respectively. Substituting these values

into equation (5), the tumour age was estimated to be approximately 58.2 days (Figure 3B).

Simulation Model 2

Invasive ductal carcinoma, histological grade II.

The tumour diameter was 10.0 mm, the mean nuclear diameter was 10.0 μm , and the nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratio (ρ) was approximately 0.55. The cellular area fraction (α) was estimated to be approximately 0.74. The numbers of Ki-67–positive cells and mitotic figures were the same as in Case 2 (100 and 2, respectively). Based on equation (5), the estimated tumour age was also approximately 58.2 days.

In equation (6), the term $(\alpha\rho)^{3/2}$ represents the combined effects of cellular packing density (α) and the N/C ratio (ρ). Since their product remains constant even when interchanged, the observed similarity in estimated tumour age suggests that cellular packing density (α) and the N/C ratio (ρ) may act in a complementary manner.

Taken together, these results indicate that the model behaves in a compensatory manner against moderate variations in cellular parameters, demonstrating relative robustness. However, substantial changes in nuclear size or cellular packing density may influence the estimated tumour age.

Although the absolute time estimation in this model may depend on field sampling, future implementation of AI-based quantitative analysis across the entire tumour region may enable more stable and reproducible estimation.

Discussion

Histopathological examination has traditionally contributed to diagnosis by morphologically evaluating tissue specimens obtained through biopsy or surgical resection, after fixation in formalin or similar agents, thereby preserving the state of the tissue at the time of sampling. In recent years, the development of novel antibodies has facilitated immunohistochemical analyses, enabling more objective evaluation of tumour characteristics and progression.

Ki-67 is currently widely used as a marker for assessing tumour proliferative activity. Ki-67 is a proliferation-associated nuclear antigen, and the MIB-1 antibody—applicable to formalin-fixed paraffin-embedded (FFPE) specimens—was reported in 1992,

allowing its use in routine pathological samples [5]. Ki-67 is expressed during all phases of the cell cycle except G₀, thereby reflecting cellular proliferative activity [1].

The Ki-67 labelling index, assessed by immunostaining with the MIB-1 antibody, is widely used as an important indicator for evaluating tumour proliferation and for guiding treatment decisions [6].

On the other hand, mitotic figures represent a morphological indicator that directly reflects cells undergoing division. Quantification of mitotic figures in high-power fields under light microscopy allows assessment of tumour proliferative activity and is incorporated into histological grading systems [2]. Furthermore, the presence of atypical mitotic figures serves as an important morphological basis for the diagnosis of malignant tumours [7,8].

Although both indicators are widely used to evaluate tumour activity, reports that integrate these parameters within a temporal framework remain limited, to the best of our knowledge.

In this study, we attempted to construct a mathematical model that integrates the number of Ki-67–positive cells and mitotic figures to retrospectively estimate the timing of tumour development. Through this approach, we aimed to introduce a temporal dimension into histopathological evaluation, which has traditionally been limited to a snapshot at a single time point.

Further consideration suggests that the proportion of mitotic cells observed among Ki-67–positive cells merely reflect the fractional time occupied by the M phase within the total cell cycle duration (T). In other words, even in cases with a high Ki-67 labelling index and abundant mitotic figures, the net proliferative rate per unit time may remain low if the overall cell cycle duration (T) is markedly prolonged.

Therefore, in the absence of information regarding the actual cell cycle length (T), it is difficult to directly estimate tumour growth kinetics based solely on the Ki-67 labelling index or mitotic counts. To accurately assess the true proliferative rate, it is necessary to incorporate real-time parameters of the cell cycle, particularly the duration of the M phase, into the model.

To address this issue, the present study employed representative values for each phase of the cell cycle as reported in the literature. Representative durations reported in the

literature are approximately 6–8 hours for the S phase, 2–4 hours for the G2 phase, and approximately 1 hour for the M phase [9]. Furthermore, variability in the total cell cycle length (T) among cells has been reported to arise predominantly from differences in the duration of the G1 phase [10].

In this model, for the purpose of standardization, the duration of the M phase was fixed at 1 hour, a representative value widely accepted in the literature, and used as the temporal reference scale for mathematical formulation. Based on this assumption, Equation (3) was derived. It should be noted that this value was adopted as a representative parameter, and the impact of variability in actual tumour conditions remains a subject for future investigation.

Thus, both Ki-67 index and mitotic counts should be interpreted as time-weighted observables rather than direct measures of proliferation.

As an initial assumption of the model, tumour cells were considered to be densely and uniformly distributed in three-dimensional space within the tumour (packing assumption).

However, in actual tumour tissues, glandular structures may be preserved in well-differentiated tumours, while in poorly differentiated tumours, fibrosis and other stromal components can lead to regions with sparse tumour cell distribution. Therefore, the entire tumour volume is not necessarily occupied by tumour cells.

If Equation (4) is applied without accounting for this factor, non-cellular components within the tumour volume—such as luminal spaces and stroma—may be erroneously included as tumour cell volume. As a result, the estimated number of tumour cells, defined as “tumour volume divided by the average volume per cell,” may be overestimated. Consequently, the estimated tumour growth duration is expected to be biased toward higher values.

To address this issue, tumour cell density was incorporated into the model. Specifically, the area fraction of tumour cells evaluated under microscopy was introduced as α ($0 < \alpha < 1$), allowing correction for the actual volume occupied by tumour cells.

With regard to necrotic areas, when considered as secondary changes occurring in regions previously occupied by tumour cells, they do not necessarily require exclusion

in principle. However, in cases with extensive necrosis, the impact on the estimated values should be evaluated separately.

Furthermore, it is well known that tumour growth *in vivo* represents a dynamic balance not only of cell proliferation but also of cell loss processes such as apoptosis and necrosis [3,11]. The present model assumes a pure proliferation system as a first approximation, and these cell loss processes are not explicitly incorporated at this stage. Extension of the model to include a cell loss fraction (φ) represents an important future direction to better approximate biological reality.

Although the initial model assumes a spherical tumour for simplicity, the fundamental derivation depends only on the volume (V). Therefore, the model is not restricted by tumour shape and can be generalized to tumours of arbitrary morphology.

In the breast cancer cases presented in the Results, comparison between Case 1 and Sim-1 showed that the increase in nuclear size was compensated by a corresponding change in cell areal density (α), resulting in similar estimated tumour ages. In contrast, in the comparison between Case 2 and Sim-2, the nuclear-to-cytoplasmic ratio (ρ) and cell areal density (α) acted in a complementary manner, and the estimated values were again nearly identical. These findings suggest that cell size, N/C ratio, and tumour packing (cell packing) interact with each other and collectively influence tumour age estimation.

Although the present study was validated using breast cancer cases, the model is constructed based on geometrical and dynamical parameters, including cell volume, cell density, and proliferative kinetics. Therefore, in principle, the model is applicable to other solid tumours. However, differences in proliferative characteristics and the extent of cell loss among tumour types may influence the estimated values; thus, tumour-specific validation remains a subject for future investigation.

Furthermore, the present model is subject to technical limitations related to field-of-view sampling. However, the future implementation of AI-based automated quantification across the entire tumour area is expected to enable more stable and reproducible estimations.

Variability in the duration of the G1 phase in tumour cells may influence their morphological features. High-proliferation tumours have been reported to exhibit

shortening of the G1 phase, reflecting disruption of cell cycle regulation [12,13]. In addition, experimental studies in neural stem cell systems have demonstrated that shortening of the G1 phase is associated with delayed differentiation and maintenance of an immature cellular state [14].

These observations suggest that the G1 phase serves as a critical temporal window for cellular maturation, and that its shortening may constrain the acquisition of differentiated morphology. From this perspective, morphological atypia may, at least in part, represent a manifestation of insufficient maturation imposed by temporal limitations within the cell cycle.

Based on this concept, the present framework provides a means to quantitatively represent such temporal constraints from histopathological observations. Rather than treating proliferative activity and morphological features as independent parameters, this model introduces a new axis of evaluation that links time-dependent aspects of cell cycle dynamics with qualitative histological features such as atypia and immaturity.

In this context, tumour age may function not only as an indicator of proliferative activity, but also as a metric that indirectly reflects the underlying temporal structure of tumour morphology.

Future applications of this framework may include comparative analysis of estimated tumour age between in situ and invasive components, enabling quantitative assessment of changes in proliferative dynamics during tumour progression. Furthermore, this time-based approach may be extendable to the analysis of tumour cell dissemination into lymphatic flow.

Taken together, these findings support the interpretation of tumour morphology as a temporal projection of underlying cell cycle dynamics.

One limitation of the present model is the assumption that tumour growth rate remains constant from the time of tumour initiation to the present. In malignant tumours in particular, proliferative characteristics may change over time due to the accumulation of genetic alterations during tumour progression [15], which may introduce errors into the estimated values.

Accordingly, the tumour age estimated in this study should be interpreted as an effective proliferative duration under the current growth conditions, rather than the actual elapsed time since tumour initiation.

In addition, in tumours exhibiting marked cellular pleomorphism, uncertainty may arise in defining a representative value for tumour cell volume. In such cases, whether to use the average value across all tumour cells or to restrict the evaluation to proliferating cells remains an open question for future investigation.

Furthermore, dynamic tumour properties such as lymphovascular invasion are influenced not only by intrinsic tumour cell characteristics but also by microenvironmental factors [16]. For example, cell–cell adhesion, stromal architecture, surrounding immune context, and cytokine milieu may all contribute to tumour invasion and metastatic behavior. These factors may not be fully captured within the current mathematical framework. Therefore, establishing quantitative approaches to evaluate the tumour microenvironment will be an important future direction, serving as a bridge between histopathological findings and dynamical modeling.

For clinical application, parameter calibration tailored to the morphological characteristics of each tumour type may be required.

Nevertheless, the present model provides a framework that enables not only quantitative assessment of tumour proliferative activity but also estimation of the timing of tumour development. In this regard, it offers a novel theoretical basis for understanding tumour dynamics.

By introducing time as an explicit analytical dimension, this approach enables tumour morphology to be interpreted within a temporal framework, thereby linking static histopathological observations with the underlying dynamics of tumour growth.

Conclusion

In this study, we constructed a mathematical model to estimate the timing of tumour initiation—referred to here as “tumour age”—based on the Ki-67 labelling index and mitotic figures routinely assessed in pathological diagnosis. This approach enables estimation of tumour age from commonly available histopathological data and introduces a temporal dimension into pathology.

The proposed mathematical framework extends beyond quantitative assessment of tumour proliferation and provides a basis for incorporating qualitative aspects of tumour behavior.

In contrast to conventional pathological diagnosis, which tends to become increasingly complex across different organs and tumour types, the present model offers a unified mathematical framework. By enabling visualization of tumour growth within a temporal context, this approach provides a new perspective for integrating diverse biological behaviors.

Ultimately, this framework suggests that tumour morphology can be understood as a manifestation of underlying temporal dynamics, supporting a shift in pathology from a static, descriptive discipline toward a time-resolved, dynamical science.

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Figure legends

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the tumour model and field-based counting.

(A) Spherical tumour model illustrating the tumour radius (R), cellular radius (r), and tumour cell areal fraction (α) at the maximal cross-section.

(B) Schematic representation of field-based counting of Ki-67–positive cells and mitotic figures within a microscopic field. Ki-67–negative cells represent the non-proliferative fraction.

Figure 2. Schematic representation of the cell cycle and Ki-67 positivity.

Ki-67 is expressed throughout the active phases of the cell cycle (G1, S, G2, and M) but is absent in G0. The duration of the Ki-67–positive phases is denoted as T [h], whereas mitotic figures correspond to the M phase.

Figure 3. Representative fields for measurement of tumour cell nuclear diameter.

(A) Case 1; (B) Case 2. Tumour cell nuclear diameters were measured in each field and used as the cellular size parameter in the tumour age estimation model. Case 2 shows larger nuclear diameters compared with Case 1.

Figure 1.

(A)

(B)

Tumour cell
areal fraction (α)

 Measurement field

 Ki-67-positive cells

 Ki-67-negative cells

 Mitotic figures

Figure 2

Figure 3.

(A)

(B)

